

THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING ENGINEERING COMPUTER GRAPHICS THROUGH PTS (PROFESSIONAL TECHNOLOGY SYSTEM) PLATFORM.

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Annotatsiya. *Shu paytga qadar mavjud ta'lim tizimida o'qitish ustuvor sanalgan bo'lsa, ayni paytda jamiyatning axborotlashuvi davrida raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish kata ahamyat kasb etmoqda ustuvorlik – o'qishga o'rgatishga yo'naltirilgan. Shu sababdan ta'limning o'qituvchi-darslik-talaba paradigmasi talaba-darslik-o'qituvchi paradigmasi bilan o'rin almashishi zarurdir.*

OTMlarda muhandislik komp'yuter grafikasi fanini dasturlarini o'zaro qiyoslash metodi asosida o'qitish yuzasidan olib borilgan ishlarning kamchiliklari tuzatildi.

Kalit so'zlar: “raqamli texnologiya”, “ta'lim texnologiyalari”, “kompyuterli modellashtirish”, “multimedia”.

Abstract. *Until now, teaching has been considered a priority in the existing education system, but at the same time, the use of digital technologies is becoming more important in the era of information society. For this reason, it is necessary to replace the digital technology in education.*

The shortcomings of the work carried out in the field of training of engineering computer graphics science programs based on the method of mutual comparison have been corrected.

Keywords: "digital technology", "educational technologies", "computer modeling", "multimedia".

In the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the priority task of "further improvement of the continuing education system, increasing the possibilities of quality education services, continuing the policy of training highly qualified personnel in accordance with the modern needs of the labor market" [1] is defined. In the implementation of this task, the main factor in the development of the design skills of students of higher education institutions is their spatial imagination, creative activity, and the skills of designing practical issues related to the field. These qualities are important in increasing the effectiveness of graphic education.

Wide use of computers by students serves to accelerate scientific and technical development in the society and, on this basis, to achieve socio-economic development. "Introducing modern forms and methods of teaching, computer and information and digital technologies into the educational process, providing higher education institutions with modern educational and laboratory equipment and educational and methodological literature, supporting and stimulating scientific research and innovation activities, higher education institutions taking steps to organize and develop modern scientific laboratories; [2] expresses the need to implement important tasks such as training competitive personnel and being able to demonstrate their professional mobility and creativity.

Digitalization of all spheres of human activity has led to the change of centuries-old pedagogical technologies. New means of teaching forced to reconsider the main issues of pedagogy: who should be taught in the higher education system at the current stage of society's

development, what should be the content of education, what forms and methods should be used as a basis for training higher education specialists [3].

Taking into account the above, we believe that revision of the content of the subject of engineering computer graphics is one of the urgent problems in teaching this subject. It is appropriate to take into account the achievements of today's science and technology fields when reorganizing the content of engineering computer graphics.

The analysis of studies focused on the problems of teaching principles allows to distinguish didactic principles common to all subjects. All researchers come to the same stop when it comes to the nomenclature of didactic principles. But the content of these principles is interpreted differently. Such principles include:

- the principle of education and training;
- the principle of connection between theory and practice;
- scientificity principle ;
- the principle of comprehensibility ;
- the principle of compatibility and consistency ;
- the principle of consciousness and creative activity ;
- the principle of demonstrability ;
- the principle of the consistency of educational results and the development of cognitive abilities ;
- taking into account the individual characteristics of learners and the principle of collectivity of education ;
- the principle of positive emotionality of education.

If education content and procedural if we divide the sides into two, then traditional didactic principles can be conditionally divided into these two groups. The conditionality of the separation of didactic principles in this way is classified by their interrelatedness and interdependence.

As an example, we cite the conditionality of separating education, education and development processes.

The content principles of education include:

- the principle of scientificity;
- principle of comprehensibility ;
- principle of consistency;
- the principle of continuity;
- the principle of integrity;
- the principle of connection between theory and practice ;
- the principle of continuity .

Principles of content selection :

Scientific principle . M.D. Dammer [4] showed the development of the content of the scientific principle. According to the results of research, the content of this principle was first shown in 1950 by M.N.Skatkin in the form of eight requirements:

- 1) to students delivered of information scientific reliability ;
- 2) being described of events essence to open
- 3) events _ show in correlation ;
- 4) events in development and this of development sharp feature show _
- 5) learner events correct dialectic- materialist explaining giver the most important theories with introduction ;

6) in learners the world to know and a person about the power of his mind right imaginations create ;

7) in students absolute and relative truth about right thoughts create ;

8) students scientific research methods with introduction _

We are Z.K. Meretukova and We agree with A.R. Chinazirova 's opinion. "The principle of scientificity in education should take into account the fact that there is "scientific pluralism" in the component of education. A different approach to one scientific problem increases students' thinking range and encourages them to search for the truth" [5].

G. M. Chernobelska's views can be understood from the last words of her quote: "Scientific content is achieved not only by giving students ready-made knowledge, but also by introducing them to scientific research methods" [6 18-p].

Taking into account all of the above, it can be said that in the process of scientific and technical development, the amount of scientific knowledge that students should acquire is increasing, while the time allocated for studying the material remains the same. In our republic, the content of engineering graphics and the method of its teaching have not changed in the last 25 years. Since 2022, only Autodesk's AutoCAD software is used in engineering graphics and related fields of the Republic of Uzbekistan . However, students of the above-mentioned foreign higher education institutions are able to master several design programs. These programs apply to structural, functional and technological systems. We believe that it is appropriate to use only programs related to the construction system, emphasizing that higher education institutions of pedagogy should take into account the training of pedagogic personnel.

In our opinion, the best way to make the most of the time allocated to engineering computer graphics, and at the same time to train competitively, is to teach several programs related to the design system in comparison with each other.

This can be caused by the principles of operation of the programs in the construction system, their tasks, and the uniformity of the results achieved with their help. This, in turn, requires improvement of the requirements for knowledge, skills and qualifications of students within the field of engineering computer graphics.

We are an engineering computer graphics **student** :

- history of computer graphics;
- departments of computer graphics;
- Systems digital technology (PTS) that make up the department of construction graphics ;
- graphic programs working in the digital technology PTS system and their principles of operation;
- electronic image formats;
- panels of equipment used for drawing;
- he should know the algorithms for drawing the object based on its spatial position ;

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Conclusion: Based on the information presented above, the organization of independent education based on research-oriented digital technology, rather than previous, creates the basis for a student's creative approach to the task.

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